

National Fund for Basic, Strategic and Frontier Application Research in Agriculture

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Concept Note

Contact Information

Date of completion: 2010-08-31 18:56:01
Concept Note No.: 4875
PID of the Project: 649
Title of the Project: Abiotic Stress Monitoring, Forecasting and Management System
Priority Area : Abiotic stress
Name of the Institute/College: Indian Agricultural Research Institute
Name of the parent organisation: Indian Agricultural Research Institute
Type of Organization : Central Government
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Details of the Cooperating Centre Principal Investigators (CCPIs) i.e. (PIs from the Partner Institutions):

SI No.:	Full Name:	Designation:	Area of specialization:	Name of the Institution:
1	Dr. Rajni Jain	Senior Scientist	Data Mining	National Centre for Agricultural Economics and Policy Research, DPS Marg, New Delhi
2	Dr. D. V. K. N. Rao	Senior Scientist	Soil Science	Indian Grassland and Fodder Research Institute, Near Pahuji Dam, Gwalior Road, Jhansi 284003
3	Dr. Preetha Panikkar	Senior Scientist	Fisheries Sciences	Reservoir Fisheries Division, Central Inland Fisheries Research Institute, Hessarghatta Lake Post, Bangalore 560089
4	Dr. A. Sarangi	Senior Scientist	Water Resources Simulation and Modelling	Water Technology Centre, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi 110012
5	Dr. Sapna A Narula	Asst. Professor	Information and Communication Technologies	Faculty of Policy and Planning, TERI University, 10, Institutional Area, Vasant Kunj, New Delhi 110070

Status of research on the problem proposed to be addressed (please refer to only the landmark work done in the last five years, detailed references not required) and the major research gaps that you want to fill in the proposed project:

The ill effects of abiotic non-living factors like excess/deficient water availability, increase/decrease in temperature, climatic aberrations, soil salinity, sodicity, acidity, nutrient deficiency/toxicity, water pollution are causing severe stress on the earth's living organisms. Simultaneous occurrence of several abiotic stresses is most lethal to plants/animals and combination of abiotic stresses is unique and cannot be directly extrapolated from their individual response. The abiotic stress sufferer candidates, viz., agriculture, animal husbandry and fisheries are trying to endure the stress with mitigation strategies by themselves. However, it is the major challenge to human beings to manage abiotic stress on them. Though various simulation models and decision support systems (DSS) were developed to study factors affecting the earth's life, creating a desktop as well as web based DSS for management of abiotic stress by using free/open source software (FOSS) tools, semantic features for better and faster access to knowledge, integrating data from various sources viz., meteorology, research institutes, commerce, farming was not attempted. Therefore, a DSS specifically designed for assisting experts to assess abiotic stress and to take a decision, which would be the optimal & suitable countermeasure strategy is proposed. The general structure of DSS software system consists of software for implementation of available models, Geographical Information System (GIS), relational database management system and user interface. The simulation models, which are being used to predict responses to various environmental conditions and management in agriculture, fisheries and animal sciences, would be part of DSS components as unit system and support the system with a user-friendly interface between data storage, analysis tools and GIS. The proposed DSS guides the user from input

handling and selection of stress mitigation actions. The proposed project: "Abiotic Stress Monitoring, Forecasting and Management System (ASMFMS) shall involve, specialisation component, integrating interpolated meteorological data, soils & crops parameters, water resources and GIS tools. This DSS would provide quantitative descriptions, systems understanding, helps to pinpoint areas where knowledge is lacking, design of adequate & effective experiments. These steps help in management of wide range of environmental scenarios and thereby creating a framework for the design of the optimal strategies to suit various climatic, biotic and abiotic conditions. Data mining and curation of agriculture, horticulture, animal, fisheries, soil, water and weather data would be integrated as information system linking agricultural, horticultural, animal, and fishery sciences. With input and output stored in a RDBMS, the prepared data with statistical procedures produce the results on maps, which shall be used to monitor, forecast and manage abiotic stress on crops, animals and fisheries.

Proposed Duration of the Project:

48 months

Give the list of objectives (not more than 5) and objective-wise major activities:

Objectives	Activities
Design of RDBMS database and development of software	1. Designing of relational database management system for housing various data. 2. Design and development of software for linking databases, integrating various models and statistical procedures. 3. Design and development of software for web user interface. 4. Design and development of software for desktop user interface.

Objectives	Activities
Creation of database of soils, water resources & weather data	1. Creating database of different soils like normal, saline (both coastal and inland), sodic and acidic of the country. 2. Creating database of water resources in the country. 3. Creating database of weather data of the country. 4. Application of different simulation models to generate knowledge from the created databases.

Objectives	Activities
Creation of database of crops, horticulture, fisheries, in India	1. Creating an inventory of field crop distribution in different regions of the country on a temporal & climatic basis. 2. Creating an inventory of horticultural crops and forest distribution in different regions of the country on a temporal & climatic basis. 3. Creating an inventory of fisheries distribution in different regions of the country. 4. Application of different simulation models to generate knowledge from the created databases.

Objectives	Activities
Application of different simulation models to generate information and knowledge creation	1. Application of different simulation models to generate knowledge from the created databases. 2. Integration of statistical procedures with the simulation models and databases. 3. Data mining and curation of agriculture, horticulture, animal, fisheries, soil, water and weather data. 4. Creation of integrated information system linking agricultural, horticultural, animal, and fishery sciences.

Objectives	Activities
Integration of GIS with the created databases	1. Integration of GIS tools with the created databases. 2. Create different theme maps of weather variables of country using realtime satellite imagery. 3. Production of results on maps to monitor & forecast abiotic stress. 4. Implementation of available models, GIS and Reference Data Base and user interface.

Please list a maximum of five major outputs (bullet points) expected to be delivered at the end of the project:

1. Desktop and Web based Decision Support System for Abiotic Stress Management of Crops, Animals, Fisheries.
2. Creation of forecast and current status of abiotic stress maps for small unit of geographical area.
3. Possibility of management of wide range of environmental scenarios under simulated framework of design for the various abiotic conditions.
4. Development of shortterm and longterm optimal & suitable countermeasure strategy for the management of abiotic stress.
5. Concept of open source agriculture research and development for mitigating abiotic stress.

Give the Contribution of the Principal Investigator (PI) in the broad field of proposed research in not more than five bullet points, including IPRs obtained. Give full references to his/her five best publications (in peer reviewed journals) in the relevant field:

1. Currently working as co-principal investigator in the project: ICT applications in agricultural research and knowledge management (In-house Project).
2. Involved in the establishment of Eprints@IARI, an institutional repository for research publications of IARI students and

scientists.

3. Involved in organisation of free/open source software tools Koha, DSpace and OJS for IARI librarians and other scientific staff.
4. Founder secretary of the Open Access Journal of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants, the first open access journal from a society housed in an ICAR institute.
5. Associate Fellow, Free Software Foundation of India, Global Member, Internet Society – India Chapter, Chennai, Member, Open Knowledge Society, Bangalore, International Consortium for Agricultural Systems Applications, International Urban Forest Data Standards Committee, Open Web Foundation.

Publications

1. Sridhar Gutam, A K Mishra, P S Pandey, Chandrasekharan H, and Aneesa G. "Need of open access repositories for NARS in India" Current Science 98.12 (2010).
2. Guttikonda Aneesa and Gutam Sridhar. (2009). Prospects of open access to Indian Agricultural Research: A case study of ICAR. First Monday [online] 14(7).
3. Gutam Sridhar, R.V. Koti, M.B. Chetti and S.M. Hiremath. (2009). Effect of different concentrations of naphthalene acetic acid and mepiquat chloride on physiological components of yield in bell pepper Tarihal local (*Capsicum annum* L.). Journal of Agricultural Research (Quarterly). 47(1): 53-61.
4. Sridhar Gutam, Virendra Nath and G.C. Srivastava. (2008). Endogenous hormonal content during grain development in wheat. Bangladesh Journal of Agricultural Research. 33(3): 493-502.
5. Gutam Sridhar, Virendra Nath, G.C. Srivastava and Santosh Kumari. (2005). Carbohydrate accumulation in developing grains of wheat genotypes. Indian Journal of Plant Physiology. 10(2): 199-201.

Total Fund Proposed: (Rupees in Lacs) : 100 Lacs

Revenue Costs: (including RA/SRF salary, Operating costs, Travel costs etc.) 40 Lacs

Capital Cost: (equipment and absolutely essential civil works; civil works is not encouraged and should not be more than 5% of total budget in any case) 25 Lacs

Other costs: (if any including institutional charges.) 35 Lacs

The PI hereby certifies that the Concept note is being submitted with appropriate permission of the competent authorities of the institutions to which the PI and CPLs belong.

The PI also certifies that the proposal has not been submitted to any other funding agency and it does not duplicate the work of any project under NAIP as listed in the NAIP web site www.naip.icar.org.in or any ongoing project in any other organization to the best of his/her knowledge. Submission of the concept note implies that he/she agrees to the rules and regulations of the national fund.

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